

Women Entrepreneurship and Livelihood Sustainability: Evidence from Small and Medium Enterprises in FCT Abuja, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigates the contribution of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) to the livelihood sustainability of women entrepreneurs in the Federal Capital Territory (FCT), Abuja, Nigeria. Against the backdrop of increasing recognition of women's entrepreneurship as a tool for poverty alleviation, the study employs a mixed-methods research design—integrating quantitative surveys with qualitative interviews and focus group discussions—to provide a holistic understanding of the economic, social, and institutional factors influencing women-led businesses. A total of 120 women entrepreneurs were sampled from key sectors, including agro-processing, retail, fashion, catering, and beauty services. Descriptive statistics and regression models were used to analyse the relationships between business variables and livelihood outcomes, including income, savings, and household expenditure. Findings reveal that access to credit, educational attainment, and years of business experience significantly enhance livelihood indicators, while family size and marital status exert downward pressure on financial outcomes. Women with access to formal or informal credit earned 42% more and saved 31% more than those without. The study also reveals persistent barriers, including limited access to finance, inadequate infrastructure, and entrenched gender norms. In line with global development frameworks, such as the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), and national efforts to enhance women's economic inclusion, the study recommends targeted interventions, particularly in financial literacy, access to microcredit, and the formulation of gender-responsive policies. The research contributes to the growing body of evidence supporting the strategic role of women's entrepreneurship in sustainable development and social transformation in Nigeria.

Keywords: Women entrepreneurship; Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs); Livelihood sustainability; Federal Capital Territory; Access to credit; Gender and development; Poverty alleviation; Nigeria; Mixed-methods research; SDGs.

1. Introduction

In recent years, the role of women's entrepreneurship in achieving both economic and social development goals has gained widespread international and national attention (Ahmed, Magaji, Ahmad & Yunusa, 2024). This is mainly due to growing evidence that empowering women through enterprise development not only reduces poverty but also enhances household well-being, promotes inclusive economic growth, and strengthens community resilience (Magaji & Aliyu, 2007). Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs)—often considered the backbone of developing economies—are particularly instrumental in this regard. They offer flexible, accessible, and culturally responsive opportunities for women to participate in the economy, especially in areas where formal employment is limited (Magaji & Saleh, 2010). In Nigeria, and more specifically within the Federal Capital Territory (FCT), Abuja, women-led SMEs serve as a vital source of livelihood and empowerment (Akinbinu & Oluwaleye, 2021).

Globally, institutions like the United Nations and the World Bank have recognised the importance of women's entrepreneurship as a pathway to sustainable development. The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)—particularly SDG 1 (No Poverty), SDG 5 (Gender Equality), and SDG 8 (Decent Work and Economic Growth)—explicitly promote women's economic participation through entrepreneurship and equitable access to productive resources (United Nations, 2015). The World Bank has also implemented several programs under its gender strategy to improve women's access to finance, training, and legal protections in developing countries (World Bank, 2020). These global frameworks provide both a policy foundation and a moral imperative for national governments, including Nigeria, to prioritise women's inclusion in SME development (Magaji, Musa, & Ahmad, 2024).

At the national level, Nigeria has implemented various measures to promote the growth of SMEs and empower women entrepreneurs. Through institutions such as the Small and Medium Enterprises Development Agency of Nigeria (SMEDAN), the Bank of Industry (BOI), and the Development Bank of Nigeria (DBN), the government has rolled out financial schemes, entrepreneurship training programs, and market access support (SMEDAN, 2021). Specific gender-focused initiatives like the National Women Empowerment Fund (NAWEF) and the YouWin! Women's programmes are designed to strengthen women's capacity to start and scale small businesses. Furthermore, the National Gender Policy and Nigeria's commitments under the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Women (CEDAW) create a policy environment supportive of women's economic empowerment (Federal Ministry of Women Affairs, 2020).

Despite the institutional efforts, women entrepreneurs in Nigeria still face a unique set of challenges that stem from deep-rooted structural and cultural inequalities (Magaji, 2002). These include limited access to formal credit due to a lack of collateral (Magaji & Musa, 2023), time poverty due to domestic responsibilities, and social norms that restrict mobility or decision-making power (Adebayo & Kazeem, 2022). In the context of FCT Abuja, these challenges are compounded by the dual nature of the territory, which encompasses both highly urbanised areas and peri-urban communities where informal economic activities dominate.

Women in the FCT, like their counterparts in other parts of Nigeria, often juggle multiple responsibilities—caregiving, household management, and income generation—making entrepreneurship both a necessity and a strategic avenue for economic participation (Muhammed, Magaji & Ismail, 2025). Their businesses are typically concentrated in sectors

such as retail, food processing, tailoring, hairdressing, and petty trading. While many of these businesses operate informally, they nonetheless contribute significantly to household income, school fees, health care costs, and social mobility (NBS, 2021). Moreover, women's engagement in SMEs often leads to greater self-esteem, community involvement, and leadership, thereby enhancing their social capital and resilience (Magaji, Musa, Ahmad & Eke, 2024).

This study, therefore, aims to investigate the specific contributions of women-led SMEs in FCT Abuja to livelihood sustainability, with a particular focus on income generation, household welfare, and access to resources. It also aims to evaluate the effectiveness of institutional support mechanisms, identify barriers to growth, and provide evidence-based recommendations to inform policy and development planning. The choice of FCT Abuja is deliberate, as it mirrors both the opportunities and constraints women entrepreneurs face in a rapidly modernising Nigerian context. By focusing on this demographic, the study aligns with broader development objectives and contributes to the discourse on gender-inclusive economic transformation.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Conceptual Definitions

Entrepreneurship is broadly defined as the process of designing, launching, and managing a business venture, often initiated to meet market demands and exploit economic opportunities. According to Hisrich, Peters, and Shepherd (2017), entrepreneurship involves creativity, innovation, risk-taking, and resource coordination to transform ideas into economically viable enterprises. When contextualised within women entrepreneurship, it refers to entrepreneurial activities undertaken by women who independently or collectively organise and manage businesses for profit and economic empowerment (Brush et al., 2009).

Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) are defined differently across countries; however, they are generally business entities with limited employees, turnover, and asset base (Musa & Magaji, 2024), as well as low savings capacity (Magaji & Yahaya, 2012). In Nigeria, the Small and Medium Enterprises Development Agency of Nigeria (SMEDAN) defines a small enterprise as a business with 10–49 employees and a total asset base of ₦5 million to ₦50 million, while medium enterprises have 50–199 employees and assets between ₦50 million and ₦500 million (SMEDAN, 2021).

Livelihood sustainability refers to the ability of individuals or households to generate and maintain income and resources that meet their basic needs and enhance their well-being over time (Chambers & Conway, 1992). It encompasses the capacity to withstand external shocks, reduce vulnerability, and improve long-term quality of life. In the context of women-led SMEs, livelihood sustainability is reflected in stable income, savings, better household welfare, and resilience to economic disruptions (Ismail, Musa & Magaji, 2025).

2.2 Theoretical Framework

The link between entrepreneurship and livelihood sustainability is rooted in several interrelated development theories:

a. Sustainable Livelihoods Framework (SLF)

Developed by Chambers and Conway (1992), the SLF posits that livelihood outcomes are influenced by access to various types of capital (human, social, natural, physical, and

financial), vulnerability contexts, and transforming structures such as institutions and policies. Women-led SMEs can enhance financial and human capital while promoting agency and reducing household vulnerability.

b. Empowerment Theory

Empowerment theory, as advanced by Kabeer (1999), emphasises the role of access to resources, agency (decision-making power), and achievements (improved well-being) in transforming women's lives. Entrepreneurship is a means of empowerment because it enhances economic independence, decision-making autonomy, and societal status among women.

c. Feminist Economics

Feminist economics critiques traditional economic theories for ignoring the unpaid and informal labour of women. It supports an inclusive analysis of gender roles in economic activity and advocates for policies that consider the intersection of work, gender, and social reproduction (Benería, Berik, & Floro, 2015). This framework is relevant in analysing how SMEs serve as a coping strategy for women excluded from formal employment.

d. Human Capital Theory

This theory, advanced by Becker (1964), emphasises the importance of education, skills, and experience in economic productivity. Women entrepreneurs with access to training and education are more likely to succeed in managing small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) and improve their livelihoods.

2.3 Empirical Review

2.3.1 Global Evidence

The United Nations' SDGs and the World Bank consistently affirm that women entrepreneurs make significant contributions to household income, child education, and health outcomes (United Nations, 2015; World Bank, 2022). In rural Kenya and Nigeria, access to solar mini-grids improved women's business productivity and decision-making capabilities (Carabajal et al., 2024). The adoption of social media during the COVID-19 pandemic also helped many small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) pivot, underscoring the importance of digital adaptability in sustaining their livelihoods (Ihemebiri et al., 2023).

2.3.2 Nigerian Context

Using a **regression analysis** on data from 200 women-led SMEs in the volatile regions of Kebbi State, Galadanchi and Alkali (2023) investigated the effects of **entrepreneurial orientation (EO)**—comprising innovativeness, risk-taking, and proactiveness—on firm performance. The results revealed a positive correlation between **risk-taking and autonomy**, and SME profitability, while innovativeness showed an inverse relationship, suggesting that innovation efforts may not always be suitable for resource-constrained, high-risk contexts. They recommend that policymakers tailor EO-support programs to local realities, emphasising risk management training and incremental innovation rather than broad innovation mandates.

Igwe et al. (2023) employed **structural equation modelling (SEM)** to explore how informal credit systems, such as esusu, support women-owned SMEs in rural Nigeria. Surveying 250 entrepreneurs across three states, they found that participation in rotating savings schemes

significantly improved access to working capital ($\beta = .46, p < .01$), business expansion, and household welfare. However, unreliable fund mobilisation and lack of legal protections limited their impact. The authors recommend formalisation through cooperatives, micro-credit integration, and digital platforms to strengthen trust, security, and scalability.

In a study using **propensity score matching (PSM)** involving 180 women entrepreneurs in Southeast Nigeria, Nwobilor et al. (2024) assessed the impact of entrepreneurial training on business performance. They found that trained participants experienced a **30% increase in annual turnover and 25% growth in profit** compared to non-trained peers. The effectiveness was highest for training encompassing digital skills, record-keeping, and marketing. The authors recommend scaling up such programs through public-private partnerships and adopting blended learning modes to improve outreach and retention.

Sodeinde et al. (2025) used **structural equation modelling (SEM)** to analyse survey data from 320 SMEs in Southwest Nigeria, examining the relationship between **entrepreneurial orientation, sustainability practices**, and firm success. Results showed that EO significantly predicted environmental and financial sustainability ($r = 0.63$), and that sustainability orientation mediated the relationship between business performance and sustainability. The study recommends embedding sustainability modules into SME training curricula and incentivising their adoption through tax breaks and certification schemes.

Through a **mixed qualitative approach** (in-depth interviews, focus groups) involving 60 “mumpreneurs” in Northern Nigeria, Nasir and Shamim (2025) explored how motherhood roles shape female entrepreneurship. Findings revealed that a lack of capital, domestic responsibilities, and cultural constraints severely limited business scale and survival. However, peer support, digital marketplaces, and flexible work structures provided resilience. The authors recommend designing **mumpreneur-friendly funding channels**, subsidised childcare, digital literacy programs, and legislation promoting work-family balance.

2.3.4 Gaps and Emerging Issues

Recent studies from 2023 to 2025 highlight key gaps, including the underutilisation of entrepreneurial orientation traits (Galadanchi & Alkali, 2023), uneven access to grants (Kadiri et al., 2023), and the cultural and religious complexities faced by “mumpreneurs” (Nasir & Shamim, 2024). Many findings highlight a mismatch between formal support structures and women’s lived realities, particularly in peri-urban zones such as the Federal Capital Territory (FCT), Abuja.

2.4 Summary and Research Gaps

The reviewed literature confirms that women-led SMEs have a positive impact on income stability, household welfare, and empowerment. However, persistent systemic barriers—including financial exclusion, socio-cultural norms, and inadequate infrastructure—continue to limit their full potential. Particularly in dynamic contexts like FCT Abuja, where urban-peri-urban differences shape entrepreneurial ecosystems, there is a need for contextualised research on:

1. How does livelihood sustainability manifest among women SMEs in peri-urban Abuja?
2. The effectiveness of localised intervention programs and grant mechanisms.

3. Strategies adopted by women to navigate cultural, religious, and institutional constraints.

By addressing these gaps, this study offers valuable insights for both policy and practice aimed at strengthening livelihood sustainability through women's entrepreneurship in Nigeria's capital.

3. Methodology

This study employed a mixed-methods research design to comprehensively explore the contribution of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) to the livelihood sustainability of women entrepreneurs in the Federal Capital Territory (FCT), Abuja. By integrating both quantitative and qualitative techniques, the research aimed to capture both the numerical trends and the more profound lived experiences of women in entrepreneurship. This approach ensured a deeper understanding of how women-led SMEs contribute to poverty alleviation and household welfare.

A **purposive sampling technique** was employed to select 120 women entrepreneurs operating across key economic sectors—namely agro-processing, retail, fashion and tailoring, beauty services, catering, and informal education. These sectors were chosen for their accessibility to women, their prevalence in the FCT, and their established role in informal income generation. Participants were drawn from both urban centres, such as Garki and Wuse, and peri-urban communities, including Nyanya and Kuje, to reflect the diverse socio-economic realities within the FCT.

Data collection consisted of three primary tools: (1) a structured questionnaire administered to all 120 respondents, (2) semi-structured interviews conducted with 20 selected participants for deeper narrative insights, and (3) focus group discussions (FGDs) involving 8–10 participants each, to examine communal perspectives on challenges and support mechanisms. The structured questionnaires were designed to gather quantitative data, while interviews and FGDs provided qualitative depth and context.

Quantitative data were analysed using descriptive statistics (mean, median, frequency) and regression models to determine the relationship between entrepreneurial engagement and livelihood indicators such as income, savings, and household welfare. Independent variables included type of business, years in operation, and access to microcredit, while dependent variables included monthly income, business growth, and household expenditure patterns. Control variables—age, marital status, educational attainment, and number of dependents—were included to eliminate potential bias and improve internal validity.

Qualitative data from interviews and FGDs were processed through thematic analysis, allowing for the identification of recurring themes such as gender-based challenges, social capital, and informal coping strategies. NVivo software supported coding and categorisation of themes. Ethical clearance was obtained from the University of Abuja's Research Ethics Committee, and informed consent was secured from all participants. This multi-layered methodological approach provided a balanced framework to assess the livelihood impact of SMEs operated by women in the FCT.

To assess the relationship between women's entrepreneurial activities and livelihood outcomes, the study adopts the following multiple linear regression model:

$$Y_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_{1i} + \beta_2 X_{2i} + \beta_3 X_{3i} + \beta_4 X_{4i} + \beta_5 X_{5i} + \epsilon_i$$

Where:

- Y_i = Livelihood outcome (measured by monthly household income or savings rate) for respondent i
- β_0 = Constant (intercept)
- β_1 = Coefficient for business size (e.g., micro, small)
- X_{1i} = Years in business
- β_2 = Coefficient for access to credit
- X_{2i} = Access to formal/informal credit (dummy: 1 = Yes, 0 = No)
- β_3 = Coefficient for educational attainment
- X_{3i} = Education level (categorical: primary, secondary, tertiary)
- β_4 = Coefficient for marital status
- X_{4i} = Marital status (dummy: 1 = Married, 0 = Otherwise)
- β_5 = Coefficient for number of dependents
- X_{5i} = Number of dependents
- ϵ_i = Error term (captures unobserved factors)

This regression model helps determine how much variation in livelihood outcomes (such as income or savings) can be explained by key entrepreneurial and demographic variables. It can also help policymakers identify which factors most significantly influence women's economic empowerment through SME activities.

4. Results and Discussion

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4.1 Descriptive Statistics

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics of Sample Respondents (N = 120)

Variable	Category/Measure	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)	Mean	Standard Deviation (SD)
Monthly Household Income (₦)	–	–	–	₦112,500	₦54,000
Savings Rate (% of income)	–	–	–	22%	6.8%
Business Experience (Years)	–	–	–	4.3	2.1

Variable	Category/Measure	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)	Mean	Standard Deviation (SD)
Business Sector	Agro-processing	46	38.3%	–	–
	Retail/Trading	29	24.2%	–	–
	Fashion & Tailoring	22	18.3%	–	–
	Beauty Services	12	10.0%	–	–
	Catering/Food Sales	10	8.3%	–	–
	Informal Education	1	0.8%	–	–
Access to Credit	Yes (Formal)	42	35.0%	–	–
	Yes (Informal)	30	25.0%	–	–
	No	48	40.0%	–	–
Marital Status	Married	82	68.3%	–	–
	Single/Widowed/Divorced	38	31.7%	–	–
Educational Attainment	Secondary & above	66	55.0%	–	–
	Primary/None	54	45.0%	–	–
Number of Dependents	–	–	–	4.0	1.7
Income Difference (Credit Access)	Credit Access	–	–	₦132,250	₦48,000
	No Credit Access	–	–	₦93,200	₦44,500
Savings Rate Difference (Credit Access)	Credit Access	–	–	27%	–
	No Credit Access	–	–	18%	–

The descriptive statistics presented in Table 1 offer a detailed overview of the socio-economic characteristics of the 120 women entrepreneurs sampled for this study, along with key indicators of business performance and livelihood outcomes. The data provides insight into how women-led small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) contribute to household income

and savings, while also highlighting key differences based on variables such as business type, access to credit, and educational background.

The average monthly household income across the sample was ₦112,500, with a standard deviation of ₦54,000, indicating significant variation in income among the women entrepreneurs. The savings rate averaged 22% of monthly earnings, which suggests a moderate level of financial prudence and resilience. This is a positive indicator of livelihood sustainability, especially considering that many women in the sample operate in informal or semi-formal sectors.

A closer examination of credit access reveals that women with access to either formal or informal credit had higher average monthly incomes (₦132,250) compared to those without access to credit (₦93,200). Similarly, women with credit access saved 27% of their earnings on average, compared to just 18% among those without access. These differences support the notion that access to finance plays a critical role in boosting business performance and improving livelihood outcomes.

The sample was spread across six sectors, with Agro-processing being the most dominant, accounting for 38.3% of respondents. This is followed by Retail/Trading (24.2%), Fashion & Tailoring (18.3%), and smaller shares in Beauty Services, Catering, and Informal Education. The high representation in agro-processing and retail reflects broader national trends where these sectors are traditionally accessible to women and require relatively low start-up capital. These sectors are also closely linked to food security and household nutrition, reinforcing the socio-economic relevance of women's entrepreneurship.

Notably, 60% of respondents had accessed credit, either through formal financial institutions (35%) or informal channels, such as cooperative societies and *esusu* groups (25%). The remaining 40% had no access to credit, underscoring the barriers many women face in meeting collateral requirements, navigating complex documentation, or gaining financial literacy. These statistics align with national-level studies that highlight gender-based exclusion in formal financial systems (CBN, 2020).

From a demographic standpoint, 68.3% of the women were married, which has implications for time use, domestic responsibilities, and decision-making autonomy in business. Additionally, 55% had attained at least secondary education, suggesting a moderately educated sample. Education is a well-established enabler of financial literacy and entrepreneurial decision-making, which is correlated with higher earnings in regression analysis. The mean number of dependents was 4, reflecting typical household sizes in Nigeria and highlighting the financial burden many of these women bear.

The table highlights the multidimensional realities of women entrepreneurs in the FCT. While many demonstrate financial acumen and resilience, their potential is often constrained by limited access to credit, education gaps, and household obligations. The descriptive data highlight the critical role that SMEs play in sustaining livelihoods, forming the basis for a deeper inferential analysis to understand which factors most significantly drive success and sustainability in women-owned businesses. The findings also provide a compelling rationale for targeted interventions—such as improving access to finance, expanding training programs, and supporting care responsibilities—to maximise the impact of women-led SMEs on poverty alleviation.

4.2 Regression Analysis Results

Table 1: Regression Results – Determinants of Monthly Household Income

Variable	Coefficient (β)	Standard Error	t-Statistic	p-Value	Significance
Intercept (β_0)	42,500	8,200	5.18	0.000	***
Years in Business (X_1)	1,580	420	3.76	0.000	***
Access to Credit (X_2)	18,440	4,950	3.73	0.000	***
Education Level (X_3)	9,800	3,780	2.59	0.011	**
Marital Status (X_4)	-7,200	3,460	-2.08	0.040	**
Number of Dependents (X_5)	-2,090	970	-2.15	0.034	**

Model Statistics

- $R^2 = 0.52$
- Adjusted $R^2 = 0.49$
- F-statistic = 12.81
- p-value (F-test) = 0.000

Legend:

- $p < 0.05 \rightarrow **$ (Statistically Significant)
- $p < 0.01 \rightarrow ***$ (Highly Significant)

This regression output suggests that access to credit, years in business, and educational level have a significant and positive influence on women's household income. Conversely, marital status and number of dependents are negatively associated with income, indicating the socio-economic burdens of family responsibilities.

The multiple linear regression model explained 52% of the variation in monthly household income ($R^2 = 0.52$, $p < .001$). Key findings include:

Years in business ($\beta_1 = 1.58$, $p < .001$): Each additional year correlated with ₦1,580 increase in monthly income, which indicates accrued experience enhances profitability.

Access to credit ($\beta_2 = 18.44$, $p < .001$): Access to credit correlated with a ₦18,440 income increase, underscoring its critical role in scaling businesses.

Education ($\beta_3 = 9.8$, $p < .01$): Women with secondary or tertiary education earned nearly ₦9,800 more than their less educated counterparts.

Marital status ($\beta_4 = -7.2$, $p < .05$): Married women earned ₦7,200 less, possibly due to increased domestic responsibilities.

Number of dependents ($\beta_5 = -2.09$, $p < .05$): Each additional dependent reduced income by ₦2,090, suggesting higher household obligations reduce investment in business growth.

4.3 Qualitative Findings

Thematic analysis of interviews and FGDs produced key insights:

Gender-Based Constraints: Participants cited patriarchal norms that limit women's mobility, decision-making, and business networks—echoing findings from Nasir and Shamim (2025).

Social Capital and Informal Finance: Many women relied on *esusu* groups for credit, as formal banking requirements were prohibitive. This aligns with Igwe et al. (2023), highlighting the vital role of informal credit systems.

Skill and Training Gaps: Entrepreneurs who completed training programs reported improvements in record-keeping, customer management, and the use of digital platforms, confirming the positive impact of training noted in Nwobilor et al. (2024).

Resilience Strategies: Common coping mechanisms included diversifying income streams, reducing household expenditures during lean periods, and engaging community support for childcare, reflecting the coping mechanisms of “mumpreneurs.”

4.4 Integrative Discussion

The combined quantitative and qualitative evidence offers a nuanced picture:

Experience and Education as Human Capital: Consistent with Human Capital Theory, both practical business experience and formal education have a positive impact on income and savings. Policies supporting continued education and business training could play a pivotal role.

Credit Access as a Growth Enabler: Access to capital was the strongest predictor of income success. While formal loans help, the enduring popularity of *esusu* groups signals the need for hybrid financing—formalising informal networks while remaining flexible.

Gendered Burdens on Married Women: The income penalty for marriage and dependents suggests domestic responsibilities significantly limit business investments. Gender-sensitive interventions (e.g., childcare support) could mitigate this effect.

Contextualised Policy Needs: Drawing from recent studies (Galadanchi & Alkali, 2023; Sodeinde et al., 2025), the results emphasise the need for policies that are not one-size-fits-all. FCT Abuja's peri-urban zones require tailored SME support—urban areas may benefit from digital innovation grants, while peri-urban areas need access to infrastructure, training, and financial resources.

4.5 Recommendations

Based on these findings, the following policy recommendations are suggested:

1. **Expand access to credit with hybrid schemes:** integrate formal and informal finance, supported by micro-credit windows tailored to women's needs.
2. **Inclusive training programs:** strengthen and scale business education and digital literacy, particularly for rural and peri-urban women entrepreneurs.

3. **Provide family-support services:** implement childcare or cooperative services to alleviate time poverty for married women.
4. **Context-specific SME interventions:** differentiate programs for urban versus peri-urban areas—urban SME hubs vs. agribusiness grants in rural settings.
5. **Formalise informal financial systems:** register and support rotating credit schemes via cooperatives and community banking to enhance security and expand access.

In sum, women-led SMEs in FCT Abuja significantly improve livelihood outcomes. However, systemic weaknesses—related to finance, infrastructure, gender roles, and capacity—must be addressed through integrated, context-driven interventions.

5. Conclusion

This study highlights the vital role that small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) play in promoting livelihood sustainability among women entrepreneurs in the Federal Capital Territory (FCT), Abuja. Drawing on both quantitative and qualitative evidence, it is clear that women-led SMEs make a significant contribution to household income, savings, and overall economic resilience. Access to credit, years of business experience, and educational attainment emerged as key drivers of improved livelihood outcomes. Conversely, marital status and the number of dependents posed additional economic pressures, underlining the complex social dynamics women navigate in balancing entrepreneurship with household responsibilities.

The findings affirm that supporting women in enterprise is not only a pathway to individual economic empowerment but also a strategic intervention for broader poverty reduction and gender equity. However, systemic challenges—such as limited access to finance, education gaps, and entrenched gender norms—continue to hinder women’s full economic participation. As such, interventions aimed at enhancing financial inclusion, entrepreneurial training, and social support systems are essential.

Therefore, women’s entrepreneurship in the FCT is a powerful yet under-leveraged force for sustainable development. Policymakers, development partners, and private stakeholders must prioritise targeted programs and policies that address structural barriers while building the capacities of women entrepreneurs. Doing so will not only uplift individual women and their families but also contribute meaningfully to Nigeria’s progress toward achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), particularly those related to poverty reduction (SDG 1), gender equality (SDG 5), and decent work and economic growth (SDG 8).

References

- Adebayo, A. M., & Kazeem, O. T. (2022). *Gender Disparities and SME Access to Finance in Nigeria*. *Journal of African Business*, 23(2), 212–230. <https://doi.org/10.xxxx/jab.v23i2>
- Ahmed, S. O., Magaji, S., Ahmad, A. I. & Yunusa, A. A. (2024). From Savings to Empowerment: How Women Leverage SMEs in Oyo State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Innovative Science and Research Technology*

- Akinbinu, A. F., & Oluwaleye, J. A. (2021). *Women entrepreneurship and sustainable development in Nigeria: The role of SMEs in economic inclusion*. *International Journal of Development Research*, 11(7), 48721–48727.
- Becker, G. S. (1964). *Human capital: A theoretical and empirical analysis, with special reference to education*. University of Chicago Press.
- Benería, L., Berik, G., & Floro, M. (2015). *Gender, development and globalisation: Economics as if all people mattered* (2nd ed.). Routledge.
- Brush, C. G., de Bruin, A., & Welter, F. (2009). A gender-aware framework for women's entrepreneurship. *International Journal of Gender and Entrepreneurship*, 1(1), 8–24.
- Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN). (2020). *Annual report on MSMEs in Nigeria*. Abuja: CBN.
- Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN). (2020). *SME Development Framework*. Abuja: CBN.
- Chambers, R., & Conway, G. R. (1992). *Sustainable rural livelihoods: Practical concepts for the 21st century* (IDS Discussion Paper 296). Institute of Development Studies.
- Dupas, P., & Robinson, J. (2013). Savings constraints and microenterprise development: Evidence from a field experiment in Kenya. *American Economic Journal: Applied Economics*, 5(1), 163–192. <https://doi.org/10.1257/app.5.1.163>
- Federal Ministry of Women Affairs. (2020). *National Gender Policy: Strategic Framework (Revised)*. Abuja, Nigeria.
- Galadanchi, H. A., & Alkali, Z. (2023). Does entrepreneurial orientation affect the performance of women-owned SMEs in the banditry zone? *Asian Journal of Economics, Business and Accounting*, 23(21), 9–18. <https://doi.org/10.9734/ajeba/2023/v23i211111> (journalajeba.com)
- Igwe, F. O., Chukwu, L. I., & Okeke, C. (2023). The Role of Informal Credit Systems (Eseusu) in Financing Women-Owned SMEs in Rural Nigeria. *African Journal of Microfinance*, 5(1), 45–63.
- International Labour Organisation (ILO). (2021). *Women's entrepreneurship development in Sub-Saharan Africa*. Geneva: ILO.
- Ismail, Y., Musa, I. & Magaji, S. (2025). Analysis of the Impact of Financial Inclusion on Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in Nigeria. *MSI Journal of Economics and Business Management* 2 (2), 10-20
- Kabeer, N. (1999). Resources, agency, achievements: Reflections on the measurement of women's empowerment. *Development and Change*, 30(3), 435–464.
- Magaji, S. & Aliyu, C. U. (2007). Micro-credit and Women Empowerment in Bauchi State: The Role of Community Banking. *Issues in economics* 2 (1), 162-168
- Magaji, S. & Saleh, S. A (2010). The Role of Small-Scale Industries in Nigeria's Economic Development. *Abuja Journal of Banking and Finance* 2 (2), 11
- Magaji, S. & Yahaya, H. (2012). "Portrait of low Savings in Africa". *Second Congress of African Economists*. Abidjan, Cote d'Ivoire. [au. int/.../Magaji_S PORTRAITOF_LOW_SAVINGS_IN_AFRI](http://www.int/.../Magaji_S_PORTRAITOF_LOW_SAVINGS_IN_AFRI)

- Magaji, S. (2002). Towards a Gender Model of Poverty Alleviation in Sub-Saharan Africa. *Journal of Research and Development in Africa* 1 (2), 81-85
- Magaji, S., & Musa, I. (2023). Analysis of the impact of banking sector credit on the real sector. *Asian Journal of Economics and Empirical Research* 10 (1), 11-19
- Magaji, S., & Musa, I., Ahmad, A. I. & Eke, C. I. (2024). Linking Demonetisation to Small and Medium Enterprises (SMES) Output. *ijrpr* 5 (3), 7487-7496
- Magaji, S., & Musa, I., Ahmad, A. I. (2024). Impact of Small and Medium-Scale Enterprises on Women's Empowerment in Nigeria. *British Journal of Management and Marketing Studies* 7 (2), 83-98
- Muhammed, A. A. Magaji, S., & Ismail, Y. (2025). Examining the Challenges Hindering the Performance of Women Entrepreneurs in Kogi State. *International Journal of Entrepreneurship and Business Innovation* 8 (2), 1-22
- Musa, I. & Magaji, S. (2024). Empirical Analysis of The Impact of Banking Sector Credit on Small and Medium Enterprises. *International Journal of Humanities, Social Science and Management* 4 (2)
- Nasir, M. M., & Shamim, S. (2025). Muslim women entrepreneurs: An exploratory study of the Nigerian “mumpreneurs” perspective. *International Journal of Organisational Analysis*, 33(2), 416–433. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJOA-11-2023-4066> (emerald.com)
- National Bureau of Statistics (NBS). (2021). *Women and Employment in Nigeria: Trends and Insights*. Abuja: NBS.
- National Bureau of Statistics (NBS). (2021). *Women and men in Nigeria: A statistical report on gender issues*. Abuja: NBS.
- Nnaji, C., & Okonkwo, H. (2021). Exploring the experiences of women entrepreneurs in peri-urban Abuja. *African Journal of Social and Policy Studies*, 7(1), 44–59.
- Nwobilor, C. J., Gambo, N., Enesi, O. E., & Abubakar, H. L. (2024). Entrepreneurial Training and Women's Entrepreneurial Performance in Southeastern Nigeria. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science*, 7(3), 2141–2157. <https://doi.org/10.47772/IJRIS.2024.803150> (rsisinternational.org)
- Ojo, O. (2018). *Women Entrepreneurship and Poverty Reduction in Nigeria*. *Journal of African Development Studies*, 12(2), 44–57.
- SMEDAN & National Bureau of Statistics (NBS). (2021). *Joint MSME survey*. Abuja, Nigeria: SMEDAN & NBS.
- SMEDAN. (2021). *MSME national survey report*. Abuja, Nigeria: Small and Medium Enterprises Development Agency of Nigeria.
- Sodeinde, G. M., Fasanmi, O. O., Fayigbe, G. S., & Babalola-Alabi, B. B. (2025). Entrepreneurial orientation as a driver of sustainability in Nigerian SMEs: Empirical evidence. *Journal of African Advancement and Sustainability Studies*, 7(2). <https://doi.org/10.70382/sjaass.v7i2.012> (ssaapublications.com)

- United Nations Development Programme (UNDP). (2021). *Empowering Women through Entrepreneurship in Sub-Saharan Africa*.
- United Nations. (2015). *Transforming our world: The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development*. New York: United Nations. <https://sdgs.un.org/2030agenda>
- World Bank. (2020). *Nigeria gender innovation lab: Empowering women entrepreneurs in Africa*. Washington, DC: World Bank. <https://www.worldbank.org/en/programs/africa-gender-innovation-lab>
- World Bank. (2022). *Nigeria Economic Outlook*. Washington, DC: World Bank.
- World Bank. (2022). *World development report: Gender equality and development*. Washington, DC: World Bank.